

Corporate Social Responsibility - A Growing Conviction in Kalyan Karnataka Road Transport Corporation

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Abstract

Corporate social responsibility is not a new issue. The main aim of a company is to minimize the costs and maximize profits. On the other hand, ethical business people recognize their responsibility to the public and to themselves. Fulfillment of these responsibilities constitutes ethical and socially responsible behavior. Although corporate social performance (CSP) has been used for several years in the business and society literature, in many cases it has been used synonymously with corporate social responsibility, corporate social responsiveness, or any other interaction between business and the social environment. This study will briefly examine the corporate social responsibility, the performance and reporting issues. Corporate Social Responsibility is the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families as well as of the local community and society at large The same report gave some evidence of the different perceptions of what this should mean from a number of different societies across the world.

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Introduction

Society gets upset when the social cost of or for that matter any business exceeds the social benefit derived from the business. Over the years since the dawn of industrial revolution and particularly after the 1950s, the activities of the corporations have been increasingly affecting the society by way of environmental pollution which include air, water and sound, ozone depletion and overcrowding on account of unplanned industrialization society expect corporation to limit activities which produce harmful effects and correct the problem that are a result of their previous actions. Social reaction to mindless industrial activity gave rise to the concept of corporate social responsibility. Over the years, it has become obvious that the desire to make a fortune must be executed within the laws of the society. During the 1960s, social activists and environmental groups campaigned for a broader notion of corporate social responsibility. The clash between the economic operation of businesses and the changing social values brought questions of social responsibility to the fore-front. The economic performance of business and the social aspects of business behavior were found to be divergent. In order to enforce corporate social responsibility, Corporate should help solve some of the social problem because businesses are influenced by the society through government policy and business thrive or starve along with society. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) refers to strategies corporations or firms conduct their business in a way that is ethical, society friendly and beneficial to community in terms of development. This article analyses the

meaning of CSR based on some theories available in literature. Corporate social responsibility is not a new issue. The main aim of a company is to minimize the costs and maximize profits. On the other hand, ethical business people recognize their responsibility to the public and to themselves. Fulfillment of these responsibilities constitutes ethical and socially responsible behavior. Although corporate social performance (CSP) has been used for several years in the business and society literature, in many cases it has been used synonymously with corporate social responsibility, corporate social responsiveness, or any other interaction between business and the social environment It is argued that three theories namely utilitarian, managerial and relational theories of CSR supported by works of other scholars in the area could be used to suggest that CSR becomes an international concern due to globalized nature of business that knows no border. CSR is evolving in its meaning and practice. This study will briefly examine the corporate social responsibility, the performance and reporting issues. Corporate Social Responsibility is the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families as well as of the local community and society at large The same report gave some evidence of the different perceptions of what this should mean from a number of different societies across the world.

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development because the very logic of CSR is towards seeing its impact in community socially, environmentally and economically. Competencies required by CSR managers are also analyzed in order to have a better understanding of the practical aspects of CSR. Finally, conclusions and implications for future research are discussed.

History of Corporate Social Responsibility

The nature and scope of corporate social responsibility has changed over time. The concept of CSR is a relatively new one—the phrase has only been in wide use since the 1960s. But, while the economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary expectations placed on organizations may differ, it is probably accurate to say that all societies at all points in time have had some degree of expectation that organizations would act responsibly, by some definition.

In the eighteenth century the great economist and philosopher Adam Smith expressed the traditional or classical economic model of business. In essence, this model suggested that the needs and desires of society could best be met by the unfettered interaction of individuals and organizations in the marketplace. By acting in a self-interested manner, individuals would produce and deliver the goods and services that would earn them a profit, but also meet the needs of others. The viewpoint expressed by Adam Smith over 200 years ago still forms the basis for free-market economies in the twenty-first century. However, even Smith recognized that the free market did not always perform perfectly and he stated that marketplace participants must act honestly and justly toward each other if the ideals of the free market are to be achieved.

In the century after Adam Smith, the Industrial Revolution contributed to radical change, especially in Europe and the United States. Many of the principles espoused by Smith were borne out as the introduction of new technologies allowed for more efficient production of goods and services. Millions of people obtained jobs that paid more than they had ever made before and the standard of living greatly improved. Large organizations developed and acquired great power, and their founders and owners became some of the richest and most powerful men in the world. In the late nineteenth century many of these individuals believed in and practiced a philosophy that came to be called "Social Darwinism," which, in simple form, is the idea that the principles of natural selection and survival of the fittest are applicable to business and social policy.

This type of philosophy justified cutthroat, even brutal, competitive strategies and did not allow for much concern about the impact of the successful corporation on employees, the community, or the

larger society. Thus, although many of the great tycoons of the late nineteenth century were among the greatest philanthropists of all time, their giving was done as individuals, not as representatives of their companies. Indeed, at the same time that many of them were giving away millions of dollars of their own money, the companies that made them rich were practicing business methods that, by today's standards at least, were exploitative of workers.

Around the beginning of the twentieth century a backlash against the large corporations began to gain momentum. Big business was criticized as being too powerful and for practicing antisocial and anticompetitive practices. Laws and regulations, such as the Sherman Antitrust Act, were enacted to rein in the large corporations and to protect employees, consumers, and society at large. An associated movement sometimes called the "social gospel," advocated greater attention to the working class and the poor. The labor movement also called for greater social responsiveness on the part of business. Between 1900 and 1960 the business world gradually began to accept additional responsibilities other than making a profit and obeying the law.

In the 1960s and 1970s the civil rights movement, consumerism, and environmentalism affected society's expectations of business. Based on the general idea that those with great power have great responsibility, many called for the business world to be more proactive in (1) ceasing to cause societal problems and (2) starting to participate in solving societal problems. Many legal mandates were placed on business related to equal employment opportunity, product safety, worker safety, and the environment. Furthermore, society began to expect business to voluntarily participate in solving societal problems whether they had caused the problems or not. This was based on the view that corporations should go beyond their economic and legal responsibilities and accept responsibilities related to the betterment of society. This view of corporate social responsibility is the prevailing view in much of the world today.

The sections that follow provide additional details related to the corporate social responsibility construct. First, arguments for and against the CSR concept are reviewed. Then, the stakeholder concept, which is central to the CSR construct, is discussed. Finally, several of the major social issues with which organizations must deal are reviewed.

The Concept

The concept of CSR is underpinned by the idea that corporations can no longer act as isolated economic entities operating in detachment from broader society. Traditional views about competitiveness, survival and profitability are being

swept away The emerging concept of CSR goes beyond charity and requires the company to act beyond its legal obligations and to integrate social, environmental and ethical concerns into company's business process. What is generally understood by CSR is that the business has a responsibility – towards its stakeholders and society at large – that extends beyond its legal and enforceable obligations.

The triple bottom line approach to CSR emphasizes a company's commitment to operating in an economically, socially and environmentally sustainable manner. The emerging concept of CSR advocates moving away from a 'shareholder alone' focus to a 'multi-stakeholder' focus. This would include investors, employees, business partners, customers, regulators, supply chain, local communities, the environment and society at large. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) promotes a vision of business accountability to a wide range of stakeholders, besides shareholders and investors. Key areas of concern are environmental protection and the wellbeing of employees, the community and civil society in general, both now and in the future.

India is making a transformational progress. The world is looking at us as one of fastest emerging economies of world. Our society is also progressing at the same rate as the economy is growing or there is a gap between economic v/s social progresses of the country. If society is progressing at the same pace as the economy is growing then it is a very healthy sign but if there is a mismatch between the two then it would be very grave situation since it may widen the gap between the different strata of the society. When most societies are wrestling with an acceleration and intensification of social change, there is a revolution of rising expectations.

There are various measures to bring about such changes in the form of war, revolution or planned way. But in India we believe in democracy, rationality and progress. But question arises whether the initiatives taken by government for social upliftment is sufficient or private players should also contribute or government, corporate and citizen's together act for this change. This paper is an attempt to answer such critical questions.

Here an attempt is being made to find economic vs. social progress and will try to suggest how Corporate Social Responsibility can contribute. It would also try to highlight the existing examples of owning social responsibilities by corporate and how they have benefited through it.

Objectives of the Study

The paper has been prepared by keeping in mind the following objectives;

They are as follows:

1. To emphasize on the history of corporate social responsibility
2. To study the key component of the corporate social responsibility in general.
3. To understand some of the drivers pushing business towards Corporate Social Responsibility.
4. To know the some of the positive outcomes that can arise when businesses adopt a policy of social responsibility.
5. To understand the concept of CSR
6. To find out the scope of CSR
7. To know how the NEKRTC has fulfilled its responsibility towards all stakeholders; what specific activities, programs and strategies it has set, devised and implemented for the same.

Review of Literature

The concept of CSR originated in the 1950's in the USA but it became prevalent in early 1970s . At that time US had lots of social problems like poverty, unemployment and pollution. Consequently a huge fall in the prices of Dollar was witnessed. Corporate Social Responsibility became a matter of utmost importance for diverse groups demanding change in the business. During the 1980's to 2000, corporations recognized and started accepting a responsibility towards society. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) focuses on the wealth creation for the optimal benefit of all stakeholders – including shareholders, employees, customers, environment and society. The term stakeholder means all those on whom an organization's performance and activities have some impact either directly or indirectly. This term was used to describe corporate owners beyond shareholders as a result of a book titled Strategic management: a stakeholder approach by R. Edward Freeman in the year 1984 According to Bowen, —CSR refers to the obligations of businessmen to pursue those policies to make those decisions or to follow those lines of relations which are desirable in terms of the objectives and values of our society. **Frederick (1960)** stated _Social responsibility means that businessmen should oversee the operation of an economic system that fulfills the expectations of the people. **Davis (1960)** argued that social responsibility is a nebulous idea but should be seen in a managerial context. He asserted that some socially responsible business decisions can be justified by a long, complicated process of reasoning as having a good chance of bringing long-run economic gain to the firm, thus paying it back for its socially responsible outlook. An ideal CSR has both ethical and philosophical dimensions, particularly in India where there exists a wide gap between sections of people in terms of income and standards as well as socio-economic status (**Bajpai, 2001**). **Goyder(2003)** argues: Industry in the 20th century

can no longer be regarded as a private arrangement for enriching shareholders. It has become a joint enterprise in which workers, management, consumers, the locality, govt. and trade union officials all play a part. If the system which we know by the name private enterprise is to continue, some way must be found to embrace many interests whom we go to make up industry in a common purpose. CSR implies some sort of commitment, through corporate policies and action. This operational view of CSR is reflected in a firm's social performance, which can be assessed by how a firm manages its societal relationships, its social impact and the outcomes of its CSR policies and actions (Wood, 1991)

1. The decrease role of government

In the past, governments have relied on legislation and regulation to deliver social and environmental objectives in the business sector. Shrinking government resources, coupled with a distrust of regulations, has led to the exploration of voluntary and non-regulatory initiatives instead.

2. Demands for greater disclosure

There is a growing demand for corporate disclosure from stakeholders, including customers, suppliers, employees, communities, investors, and activist organizations.

3. Augmented customer interest

There is evidence that the ethical conduct of companies exerts a growing influence on the purchasing decisions of customers. In a recent survey by Environs International, more than one in five consumers reported having either rewarded or punished companies based on their perceived social performance.

4. Competitive labour markets

Employees are increasingly looking beyond paychecks and benefits, and seeking out employers whose philosophies and operating practices match their own principles. In order to hire and retain skilled employees, companies are being forced to improve working conditions.

5. Supplier relations

As stakeholders are becoming increasingly interested in business affairs, many companies are taking steps to ensure that their partners conduct themselves in a socially responsible manner. Some are introducing codes of conduct for their suppliers, to ensure that other companies' policies or practices do not tarnish their reputation.

Some of the positive outcomes that can arise when businesses adopt a policy of social responsibility include: Towards itself It is the responsibility of each corporate entity run business and to work towards growth, expansion and stability and thus earn profits. If the corporation is to achieve social and economic ends, organizational efficiency should be boosted up. Responsibilities towards Employees

are the most important part of an organization. Following are some of the responsibilities which a business entity has towards its employees- Timely payment

1. Hygienic environment
2. Good and impartial behavior
3. Health care through yoga
4. Recreational activities
5. Encouraging them to take part in managerial decisions
6. Responsibility towards shareholders
7. It is the responsibility of corporate entity to safeguard the shareholders' investment and make efforts to provide a reasonable return on their investment.

Responsibility towards state Out of the profit available, the state is entitled to a certain share as per the income tax laws. Utmost transparency has to be exerted regarding the profit & loss account and the balance sheet.

Responsibility towards consumers The Company should maintain high quality standards at reasonable prices. It should not resort to malpractices such as hoarding and black marketing. Responsibility towards environment It is the responsibility of the organization to contribute to the protection of environment. It should produce eco -friendly products. Moreover, industrial waste management must be taken care of.

Profile of Study Unit

The Government of Karnataka under order No. HTD 65 TRA 99 (i) dated 04-08-2000, constituted a new Road Transport Corporation under section 3 of the Road Transport Corporation Act 1950, called North Eastern Karnataka Road Transport Corporation (NEKRTC) with its headquarters at Gulbarga with effect from 15-08-2000. While inaugurating the Corporation the then Chief Minister of Karnataka Sri. S.M. Krishna remarked that, "the advent of the NEKRTC is a milestone in the development of the transport network in the Hyderabad Karnataka region." Inaugurating the NEKRTC, he hoped that "the decision of the State Government to split the KSRTC and constitute the NEKRTC would help remove the feeling that the government was neglecting the region."¹⁵ NEKRTC was established on 1.10.2000 having been separated from KSRTC for providing "adequate, efficient, economic and properly coordinated road transport services" in the North eastern part of the state of Karnataka. Availability of adequate, safe and comfortable passenger transport facility is a very important index of economic development of any country. Public transport provides the vital connectivity in a developing society. NEKRTC is operating 3718 schedules covering 12.74 lakh kms carrying 12.00 lakh passengers every day. NEKRTC is serving 92%

of the villages in its area (3859 out of 4203) with transport facility. NEKRTC's Infrastructure - one corporate office, 09-Divisional offices, 47 Depots, 122 bus stands and 4356 buses.

Present Size of the Organization

1. Number of buses (As on 31-03-2021) :4653
2. Number of employees (As on 31-03-2021) :19629
3. Number of depots : 52
4. Number of bus shelters :1173
5. Total bus stations : 122
6. No. of passengers transported daily (up to Apr 2013) :4836.25 Lakh
7. Total number of routes (April 2021) : 3641
8. Zonal Work Shops: 02
9. Bus Body Building Unit : 1
10. Tire Retreading Shops : 7
11. Staff Training Colleges : 2

Corporate Philosophy of Kalyan Karnataka Road Transport Corporation

1. To provide safe, clean, comfortable, punctual and courteous commuter service at an economic fare.
2. To provide employee satisfaction in financial and humanistic terms.
3. To strive towards financial self-reliance in regard to performance and growth.
4. To attain a position of reputation and respect in the society

Csr and Nekrtc Drivers' Awareness Programs:

The following are the CSR Adopted by KKRTC

1. 50% concession on fares is provided to drama troupes/yakshagana troupes sponsored by the Karnataka Sangeetha Nataka Academy.
2. Home guards (in uniform) are allowed to travel free in city services while on duty.
3. Blind persons are issued with free pass to travel in mofussil, sub-urban and city services throughout the state.
4. Physically handicapped persons are issued with concessional pass to travel from their native place up to 100 kms.
5. Unrestricted free travel facility is extended to freedom fighters throughout the state. One assistant is allowed to accompany the freedom fighter who is aged 75 years and above, free of cost.
6. Free travel facility to Goa freedom fighters throughout the state. One assistant is allowed to accompany the Goa freedom fighter who is aged 75 years and above, free of cost.
7. 25% concession on fares is provided to senior citizens aged 60 years and above in ordinary/express/Rajahamsa services, including inter-state services.
8. Monthly passes are issued at the rate of Rs. 700 per month in city services to general public.
9. Chartered contract services are provided to schools and colleges on concessional rates at

Rs. 35 per km. for school students and Rs. 36 per Km. for college students. For industries, Karnataka Sarige bus contract rate is Rs. 37 per Km. and for ultra-deluxe is Rs. 43 per km. 10 Widows/Wives of freedom fighters are issued with free journey coupons of Rs. 2000 per annum.

10. The children who were honoured by the Central Government with "Shourya Prashasti" are issued free pass to travel in mofussil, city/sub-urban, express, Rajhamsa services throughout the state, until they attain the age of 18 years.
11. Free travel facility is provided to recognized press persons in any class of Services within the Karnataka State.
12. Free passes are issued to the dependents of Martyr's. This facility is extended in ordinary and express services within the state to the dependents i.e., father, mother, wife and dependent children for a period of 10 years (from July 2012 to July 2022).
13. 16.20% and 6.55% of commercial stalls in bus stations are reserved for SC & ST, respectively.
14. 10% of reservation is provided to physically challenged persons in appointment of franchise for advance reservation counters in the state.
15. 10% of total commercial stalls at bus stations are reserved for physically challenged persons.
16. All telephone booths in bus stands are reserved for visually impaired persons (100% blind persons).
17. Discount of 5% on fare is offered, if advance reservation is done for a group of 4 and more passengers.
18. Discount of 10% on return journey fare is offered, if any passenger books tickets both for onward and return journey simultaneously.
19. The computerised Public Information System (PIS) was introduced in 60 bus stations in the Corporation.
20. Daily pass in city services was introduced in the cities/towns of Kalaburagi, Yadagiri, Bidar, Vijayapura, Hosapete, Koppala, Raichuru and Ballari. The rate of Day Pass in Kalaburagi is Rs.40
21. Concession for NEKRTC Employees: a) As per the industrial truce settlement, all class III & IV employees are issued with free passes to travel between their residence and place of work & back, in city and sub-urban services. b) Free family pass without restriction of distance is issued to employees and their family once in a year. c) The children of NEKRTC employees are issued free passes upto 12th stage in city and mofussil services to travel between residence and place of school/college and back. h) Public Complaints: 292 complaints received from the public during the year were

investigated and suitable action taken wherever warranted. In all, 255 complaints were disposed of and remaining 37 complaints were under different stages of disposal as at the end of the year. Suggestions received from commuters for improvement of services were given due consideration and appropriate action taken to implement them wherever found feasible. i) Special Services for Jathras/Fairs: The Corporation operated special services on special occasions like fairs, jathras, religious, cultural and social celebrations in all operating divisions to meet additional transport needs as was done during previous years.

Natural calamities: During the time of scarcity and drought, flood, cyclone etc. NEKRTC does its duty towards the society through donations and transportation of relief goods and food to the affected.

1. Corporation benefits:

1. Enhanced financial performance;
2. Lesser operating costs;
3. Enhanced brand image and reputation;
4. Increased sales and customer loyalty;
5. Better productivity and quality;
6. More ability to attract and retain employees;
7. Reduced regulatory oversight;
8. Access to capital;
9. Workforce diversity;
10. Product safety and decreased liability.

2. Benefits to the community and the general public:

1. Charitable contributions;
2. Employee volunteer programmes;
3. Corporate involvement in community education, employment and homelessness programmes;
4. Product safety and quality.

3. Environmental benefits:

1. Greater material recyclability;
2. Better product durability and functionality;
3. Greater use of renewable resources;
4. Integration of environmental management tools into business plans, including life-cycle assessment and costing, environmental management standards, and eco-labelling.

Conclusion

It is now recognized that poverty reduction and sustainable development will not be achieved through government action alone. Policy makers are paying increasing attention to the potential contribution of the private sector to such policy objectives. The concept of CSR is sometimes used as shorthand for businesses' contribution to sustainable development. A number of core development issues are already central to the international CSR agenda. They include labour standards, human rights, education, health, child labour, poverty reduction, conflict and

environmental impacts. Thus Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is about how companies manage the business processes to produce an overall positive impact on society. Thus companies consider the interests of society by taking responsibility for the impact of their activities on customers, suppliers, employees' shareholders, communities and other stakeholders, as well as the environment. This is seen to extend beyond the statutory obligation to comply with legislation as organizations are voluntarily taking further steps to improve the quality of life for employees and their families as well as for the local community and society at large. If a company chooses to follow the way of CSR, it will integrate ethical concerns in its activities and in its interaction with all the Stakeholders. This implies that the corporate units function in such a way that their CSR activities in all likelihood actually reach out to the beneficiaries –the society in general. The ethical considerations are aimed at preparing the groundwork for expecting the correct reaction or response of their CSR generated activities

References:

1. Corporate governance and social responsibility: a new sustainability paradigm
2. Bergkamp L European Environmental Law Review, 2002 .
3. Andrew crane abd dirk matten : Corporate Social Responsibility: Readings and Cases in a Global Context
4. Sanjay K. Agarwal Corporate Social Responsibility in India 4 April 2008
5. Michael E, Porter Mark R, Kranler. Strategy and Society: The Link between Competitive Advantage and Corporate Responsibility. Harvard Business Review, 2007
6. Mette Morsing, Majken Schultz. Corporate Social Responsibility Communication: Stakeholder
7. Information, Response and Involvement Strategies, Business Ethics: A European Review Volume 15 Number 4 October 2006.
8. www.kssrtc.gov.in
9. www.wikipedia.com
10. Donna J. Wood, "Corporate Social Performance Revisited," The Academy of Management Review, Vol. 16, No. 4(1991): 695.
11. Roger A. Buchholz, "Corporate Responsibility and the Good Society: From Economics to Ecology," Business Horizons (July/August 1991):
12. Richard J. Klonoski, "Foundational Considerations in the Corporate Social Responsibility Debate," Business Horizons(1991, July/August)
13. [https://kkrtc.karnataka.gov.in/storage/pdf-files/Administrative%20Reports/FINAL%20NEKRTC%20ENGLISH%20-%202014-04-2022\(1\).pdf](https://kkrtc.karnataka.gov.in/storage/pdf-files/Administrative%20Reports/FINAL%20NEKRTC%20ENGLISH%20-%202014-04-2022(1).pdf)